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Attractive places to live? Location decisions in medium-sized cities affected by shrinkage

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ABSTRACT

This article examines how a balance can be achieved between growing, congested large cities and shrinking smaller cities with rising vacancies. It argues, from the perspective of sustainable spatial development, that reusing existing vacant buildings and resources in shrinking cities is preferable to new construction and further land consumption. The contribution analyses location factors that encourage people to move to a peripheral, medium-sized city affected by shrinkage and demonstrates that such cities can serve as attractive alternatives to large cities due to available housing, spatial and social proximity, and a high quality of life.

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Medium-sized cities; location decisions; experimental approaches; sustainable spatial development

Congestion versus vacancy

Many large cities and agglomerations in Germany and Europe are destinations for national and international in-migration due to education, employment, cultural and leisure opportunities (Sander, 2014; Schmidt-Seiwert *et al.*, 2019). The increasing population numbers in these cities often lead to congestion, manifesting in rising housing prices or worsening environmental quality due to land sealing, traffic and noise pollution (Bithas & Christofakis, 2006; European Environment Agency, 2020). These often go hand in hand with a reflection on the current choice of residential location and a consideration of relocation for economic, ecological or a combination of both reasons (Müther & Waltersbacher, 2022). On the other hand, smaller cities in peripheral locations, i.e. far away from the agglomerations or tourist and natural attractions, often face the challenge of declining population. Long-lasting population losses over the past decades have led to high building vacancy rates in these cities, a deterioration of building fabric, an under-utilised and thus endangered infrastructure, municipal financial problems due to the cities' lower economic strength, and even a feeling of neglect and stigmatisation (Wiechmann & Pallagst, 2012; Chouraqui, 2021). In the future, these smaller peripheral cities will be faced different but similarly large challenges compared to large cities.

As a response to the growing housing shortage in many large cities, there is increasing demand for more rapid and extensive new construction. In 2022, the

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newly elected federal government of Germany announced the goal of building 400,000 new flats annually (Die Bundesregierung, 2022). In addition to various framework conditions that make this goal seem impossible at the moment, such an approach is also questionable from the perspective of ecological sustainability and balanced spatial development. So far, the discussion has not taken into account how existing vacancies and, above all, building resources in cities affected by shrinkage can be made usable again and thus, how new construction activities and increasing land consumption in agglomerations can be prevented (Leibniz-Institut für ökologische Raumentwicklung, 2024, Knippschild et al. 2025). Germany's polycentric urban structure offers good conditions for reducing the pressure on agglomerations in the sense of sustainable spatial development. However, not only the large cities spread across Germany should be considered, but also smaller cities within rural areas and their distinctive assets (BBSR, 2021).

Studies show that large cities are not the preferred residential locations at all if people could choose them independently of other framework conditions. However, locations with a certain urban offer are desired (Federal Foundation of Baukultur, 2016). Even before the coronavirus pandemic, but increasingly as a result of it, there have been reports of people leaving large urban centres and seeking for smaller cities and even rural areas (Stawarz *et al.*, 2022). The reasons are varied and can range from the search for cheaper housing prices to the opportunity for better personal self-development. The supposed advantages of smaller cities are often considered to be the still urban supply structure with short distances between the various institutions, the possibility to fulfil one's housing wishes, opportunities through vacant buildings and thus space for new ideas and innovations, strong social networks and a sense of active community engagement (Fertner *et al.*, 2015; Mainet & Edouard, 2018; Kroiß & Klafft, 2020).

The paper provides an analysis of households' needs and demands for a residential and living location based on location factors. The focus is on medium-sized cities due to the desire to live in a city with a suitable urban offer, but without the congestion of agglomerations. The aim of paper is to identify factors that support a location choice in a peripheral medium-sized city affected by shrinkage, and to present strengths and potentials to be promoted in these cities that contribute to them becoming alternative locations to agglomerated areas. After the introduction, the second part deals with a literature overview on medium-sized cities affected by shrinkage and location decisions. Then, data from an experimental project approach ('Testing the City – Living and Working in Görlitz') in a case study city is presented. Finally, findings are presented and discussed on how medium-sized cities in peripheral locations can use urban planning strategies to successfully position themselves in the competition for new residents and thus counteract a downward spiral often associated with these cities.

Approach and state of research

Medium-sized cities affected by shrinkage

In Germany, medium-sized cities have a population between 20.000 and 100.000 and a function as medium-sized or higher-order centres (BBSR, 2020–2023). This definition is increasingly being discussed, particularly in the context of ongoing urbanization in

a national and international context. As a result, there are arguments for classifying cities with a population between 50,000 and 250,000 as medium-sized cities (Ofori-Amoah, 2007; Servillo *et al.*, 2017).

In addition to different classifications, the medium-sized city type includes very heterogeneous cities that can differ from one another, particularly depending on their location and function. Nevertheless, the literature identifies several characteristic features – particularly regarding urban structure, community and mobility – that are common to many of these cities (see Figure 1). These cities are characterized by their spatial and social proximity. The centre with residential and working functions offers a wide range of cultural and leisure activities too (Schmidt-Lauber, 2017). Compared to large cities, the centre is usually surrounded by lower and less densely built-up areas, which often have a residential function, although a fragmentary infrastructure can already be seen in districts bordering the city centre (Adam, 2005; Servillo *et al.*, 2017). The social proximity characteristic of medium-sized cities often results in a lower degree of anonymity and more frequent spontaneous interactions in public spaces compared to large cities (Lindner, 2010; BBSR, 2012). Mobility within a medium-sized city typically consists of a flexible mix of cycling, walking and the use of cars or local public transport, facilitated by relatively short distances, especially in the inner city area, but also to neighbouring districts (Schmidt-Lauber, 2010). The local train station usually serves as a starting point for connections to the surrounding region and other cities. As the offers in the cultural, commercial and leisure sectors are usually limited, this often leads to cross-location mobility. The radius of residents extends beyond the city borders in order to take advantage of the cultural, economic or social offerings of other (larger) cities (Brabazon, 2015; Schmidt-Lauber, 2017). This study is based on the definition used by the German Federal Ministry and is therefore focussed on the German discussion context. Nevertheless, international studies and publications also show similar characteristics of medium-sized cities – as listed above – in terms of facilities, development and current challenges (Servillo, 2014; Demazière, 2017).

Figure 1. Characteristics of medium-sized cities (own illustration).

In recent years, medium-sized cities have increasingly attracted scholarly attention, however, research often fails to clearly distinguish them from small towns (Bell & Jayne, 2009). Additionally, the criteria used to differentiate between city types can vary significantly depending on the geographical context, such as their proximity to or distance from major urban agglomerations.

This article deals with medium-sized cities that have experienced shrinkage and are located peripheral, i.e. far away from large cities or agglomerations. In urban research, shrinkage is not only defined and applied to the decrease in population, but is seen as a multidimensional process with interrelated economic, social, demographic and physical-structural as well as symbolic developments (Haase *et al.*, 2014; Bernt, 2018; Chouraqi, 2021). The causes of shrinkage processes are complex and usually consist of a combination of economic structural change and the resulting loss of jobs as well as a selective migration of a primarily young and qualified population (Cunningham-Sabot & Fol, 2009). Accordingly, the effects of shrinkage processes are multidimensional and affect housing markets, urban structure, public infrastructure and the social structure of urban districts or the city as a whole. Due to a decreasing population density, increasing loss of retail and service facilities and declining financial strength of the municipalities, the urban atmosphere is increasingly lost and the feeling of being left behind increases (Wiechmann & Pallagst, 2012; Brabazon, 2015). In this study, peripheral location is based on the problem-oriented basic typology of space developed by the BBSR (2020a), which is determined using the indicators of density, accessibility and centrality. Peripheral rural areas are defined here as structurally weak regions characterized by their distance from centers, limited transportation connections, weak functional interlinkages and infrastructural deficits. The term ‘peripheral’ is used as a criterion for one-sided power and decision-making relationships as well as for spatial location. It should be distinguished from the term ‘peripherisation,’ which is understood not only as a static outlying location, but as a dynamic socio-spatial process characterized by outmigration, disconnection and dependency (Kühn *et al.*, 2017).

Shrinkage processes have been analysed for several years now. In the 2000s, the issue of shrinkage and its academic debate returned to the focus of attention, particularly with the high levels of out-migration in many communities in eastern Germany (Kemper, 2008; Haase *et al.*, 2014; Kërçuku, 2023). Over time, it was increasingly recognized that regional shrinkage processes are not limited to eastern Germany and that the demographic development of cities and regions must be addressed throughout Germany and Europe (Cunningham-Sabot & Fol, 2009; Reckien & Martinez-Fernandez, 2011). The shrinking process is now receiving more attention in the scientific debate, as it is predictable that more cities and regions will be affected by population decline due to demographic developments, which will subsequently initiate further processes of declining economic power and underutilised infrastructures (Haase *et al.*, 2014). A comparative European study that traced various trajectories of shrinking cities between 1990 and 2010 showed that 20% of cities shrank during this period and that almost 900 cities are currently shrinking (Wolff & Wiechmann, 2017).

The scientific and practice-oriented debate on shrinkage processes is increasingly recognizing that these processes must be accepted and shaped. Various concepts and ideas are being discussed, like designing new open spaces in a perforated city (Häußermann & Siebel, 2004), focusing and prioritizing future urban development

(Liebmann, 2009), demographic, economic or urban regeneration processes (Kühn & Liebmann, 2009), growth-innovation-oriented approaches (Sousa & Pinho, 2015) or concepts for reducing land consumption, post-growth and the use of existing buildings (Eckardt & Brokow-Loga, 2020).

This study is based on the assumption that peripheral medium-sized cities experiencing shrinkage can nevertheless be attractive places to live, owing to characteristics such as ample available space, spatial and social proximity and a high quality of life (Mainet & Edouard, 2018). Research has shown that quality of life in such cities is often enhanced by factors like lower housing costs, less congestion, access to green spaces and strong community ties (Steinführer, 2022; European Commission, 2023). These attributes can contribute to residents' overall well-being and satisfaction, making these cities appealing despite demographic challenges (Wesz *et al.*, 2023). However, the necessity to adapt urban space to a smaller population while simultaneously maintaining or enhancing its attractiveness for potential newcomers presents new planning challenges for affected cities (Fertner *et al.*, 2015; Haase *et al.*, 2014). Addressing these challenges requires innovative approaches to urban development that prioritize both the needs of current residents and the expectations of future inhabitants. Location decisions as complex processes

The analysis is based on the location factors known from economic geography, which are transferred to the residential location choices of households. Using various hard and soft location factors, the author analyses which factors are relevant when choosing a location. In the context of changing working environments and a shortage of skilled workers, it is increasingly being discussed that people do not only settle in a place because of the job, but that other factors also play a role. Economic geography studies on companies' choice of location show that soft factors, such as quality of life, environmental quality or housing and living environment, play an increasingly important role (Vaillant *et al.*, 2012).

The debate over the relative importance of economic factors – such as available jobs, companies and wage structures – versus location amenities – such as cultural offerings, environmental quality, social climate – influence the choice of location, especially for highly qualified people, has been going on for some time. A study by Martin-Brelot *et al.* (2010) contrasts Florida's (2012) emphasis that creative professionals are highly mobile and are primarily attracted by the soft location factors of large cities. It shows that it is above all the place of birth, family ties or the choice of place of study that make creative professionals move to a location or keep them there. Martin-Brelot *et al.* (2010) point out that job opportunities and salary prospects are included in the choice of location, as well as soft factors such as the attractiveness of a location, for example in terms of the surrounding landscape or the tolerance and openness of the urban society. The study emphasizes that people are attracted to a location by hard location factors and remain (permanently) connected to it by soft factors.

Building on findings of Martin-Brelot *et al.* (2010), other studies likewise emphasize that while labour market conditions play a central role in a location decision, quality of life considerations are becoming increasingly important, especially when it comes to retaining people in the location for the long term (Murphy & Redmond, 2009; Niodomysl & Hansen, 2010; Buch *et al.*, 2014). Shapiro (2006) showed that the growth of a city is not only driven by existing economic power, but that an improved quality of life can also

contribute to this. Also amenities are particularly important for highly qualified people, e.g. a wide range of services in close proximity, an attractive cityscape, a good social infrastructure, easy organization of everyday life thanks to a good transport infrastructure, climatic conditions or an appropriate natural environment and surrounding landscape (Arntz, 2010; Rodríguez-Pose & Ketterer, 2012; Lawton *et al.*, 2013).

Previous studies on residential location choices often focus on migration to the suburban surroundings of agglomerations and less on migration to peripheral cities (Münter, 2012; Buch *et al.*, 2014). Most studies also focus on people who have made the decision to migrate and analyse their reasons and motivations. Factors that have prevented people from deciding to move are not surveyed. This study takes a new approach to acquiring knowledge. It deals specifically with the decision to move to a peripheral medium-sized city affected by shrinkage. The particularity of the survey is that the relevance of individual location factors is examined and an evaluation is made based on the experience during a temporary stay in such a city. In this way, a decision to move can be made on the basis of much more detailed information than is usually the case with interregional migration. In addition, the empirical analysis of the present study includes both persons who have made a decision to move to a shrinking medium-sized city in peripheral locations and those who have decided against it.

The city of Görlitz and data collection within an experimental project approach

Case study: city of Görlitz

The city of Görlitz is used as a case study for the empirical part of this paper. The easternmost city in Germany is known above all for its large and well-preserved building stock. However, the city also stands as an example for peripheral medium-sized cities affected by shrinkage. In the 15 years following German reunification, the city lost almost a quarter of its population due to demographic and economic change. The population has stabilised again in recent years and is even rising slightly. Around 56,000 people currently live in the city of Görlitz (City of Görlitz, 2009, 2022; Kërçuku, 2023). The effects of the population loss still can be seen, among other things, in the comparatively high vacancy rate in the city centre. The 2022 census database determined a rate of 13% for the city. Expressed in absolute figures, the city has almost 5000 vacant flats, around half of which are directly available on the market. The typical characteristics of a medium-sized city described above can also be found in Görlitz. The city has a clearly defined urban centre that fulfils residential, working and public services functions. However, first fragmentary structures can be seen in the neighbouring districts. The city is also characterised by short distances within locations. There is a strong sense of social cohesion and interdependence among the residents of Görlitz, reflected in the numerous collaborative initiatives that engage citizens, civil society and local institutions. In recent years, a dynamic cultural and creative scene has emerged, playing an increasingly vital role in shaping the city's social and cultural landscape. Organizations such as Kühlhaus e. V., Wildwuchs e. V. and Second Attempt e. V. have become central actors in fostering community engagement, artistic expression and participatory urban development. Mobility within the city is characterised by a mix of driving, using local public

transport, cycling and walking. A railway station and a bus station provide connections to the surrounding area and the nearby cities of Dresden and Wrocław.

In the city of Görlitz, an experimental project approach was implemented to gain knowledge about the demands and opportunities of in-migration with regard to attract residents in order to revitalise existing urban areas (Knippschild *et al.*, 2020; Zöllter *et al.*, 2024). As part of the series, the project ‘Testing the City – Living and Working in Görlitz’ was implemented in the years 2018 to 2020. Interested people were given the opportunity to live and work in the city for a limited period of four weeks in order to gain their own experience and contribute new perspectives and ideas to urban development. The target group was people who are not tied to a particular location and could bring their work with them. In cooperation with local initiatives, workspaces were also offered (co-working space, workshop, showroom), thus establishing an initial connection to the local community. The project participants acted as experts and reflected on their experiences in the city. Accompanying scientific research made it possible to derive general requirements and needs for a location as well as context-related assessments of the city of Görlitz.

Methodology of the accompanying scientific research

The scientific monitoring of the project participants during the project phase from January 2019 to March 2020 consisted of a standardised online survey before their stay and a guided final interview in the last week of their stay. The standardised survey primarily focused on the current living and working situation as well as the requirements for a place to work and live. In the interview, the requirements were compared with the concrete experiences on site and the different perceptions of life in a medium-sized city were also discussed. This made it possible to compare the requirements for a location and the assessment of the city of Görlitz in detail and to analyse various aspects of location choice.

In order to include the longer-term perspective on the choice of location and the after-effects of the trial stay, the author decided to conduct an additional survey of former project participants. This survey was primarily intended to address the decision for or against a move, as well as the reflection and perhaps changed assessment of the conditions in Görlitz after returning to everyday life. The evaluation of the situation during the coronavirus pandemic also played a role in the additional survey. A further guided interview was conducted with nine participants in spring 2021, four households who had decided to move to Görlitz and five who had decided against it (Zöllter, 2023).

The mix of methods provided a very detailed insight into the opinions of the project participants. This comprehensive analysis compensates for the lack of representativeness achieved with 47 people, as it generates detailed knowledge. The context of the Görlitz case study and the target group of working people is also a limitation for generalised statements. Nevertheless, the approach is viable, as the participants’ trial stays in the city of Görlitz made it possible to analyse their assessment of the medium-sized city as a location using a specific example. This experimental approach to the project also made it possible to obtain data from people who decided not to relocate. As the project worked with an open call for applications, the participants were already an indication of the people for whom a potential residential and living location in a medium-sized city could be of interest.

Description of project participants

For the study, data was collected from 47 people who lived in Görlitz for a four-week trial period between January 2019 and March 2020. The participants included five families with a total of seven children. Children were not part of the research survey due to ethical considerations and methodological limitations. The perspectives of children were indirectly considered through parental input and observation during participatory activities. 40% of the participants were women and 60% men. The age group of 30 to 39-year-olds was the most represented at 41%, followed by 50 to 59-year-olds at 19% (see [Figure 2](#)). Almost all participants indicated an interest in the city as their motivation for taking part in the project (98%). Another frequently mentioned reason was the search for new networks (81%) or the search for a new place to live (73%).

The participants were asked to specify their areas of work. Some participants also named several sectors. Overall, it was noticeable that the majority (82%) were assigned to the various submarkets of the cultural and creative industries according to the definition of the German Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy (2020). At 21%, the largest share of participants worked in the art market, primarily in sculpture and painting. Furthermore, 14% of participants worked in the press market and 10% in the design industry. 18% of participants worked in teaching or consulting as well as in business or other areas.

The majority of participants in the ‘Testing the City’ project came from Germany (94%). 45% of participants came from Berlin and almost a quarter from the federal state of Saxony. Among the participants, 70% were people who lived in a large city with more than 100,000 people at the time of taking part in the project (see [Figure 3](#)).

More than half of the participants (57%) stated that they were ‘satisfied’ with their current housing situation, while a quarter were ‘less satisfied’. Participants were less likely to criticise their current home or residential building than the current residential location in general. Almost half of the participants (49%) stated that they were ‘not at all satisfied’ with the rents on the local housing market. Among participants living in a large city at the time of the survey, this was even two thirds. Participants were also ‘not at all satisfied’ with the opportunities to buy property (43%), the availability of housing in the city or municipality (36%), the volume of traffic in the city or municipality (34%) and the noise pollution (21%) (Zöllter, 2023).

Figure 2. Participant age groups (own illustration).

Figure 3. Participant place of residence (own illustration).

Findings

Relevant location factors

The data shows that both hard and soft location factors are relevant when choosing a place to live. Figure 4 shows a schematic illustration of the factors that emerged as significant in the empirical analysis. As it was rarely possible to identify individual factors as relevant, related location factors are grouped together in the illustration.

A key factor when choosing a place to live is the cost factor in combination with available housing, i.e. the possibility of finding (residential) space that meets individual needs and at affordable prices. The high importance of an adequate supply of housing is related to the dynamics on the stressed real estate markets of many large cities and agglomerated areas discussed in the introduction. The rents and property prices in these cities in particular have risen the most compared to other types of cities (infratest dimap, 2019; BBSR, 2020b). As many of the participants lived in a large city they expressed great dissatisfaction with the availability of housing and rental prices on the local housing market. However, the availability of housing is not enough for a city to be considered

Figure 4. Relevant factors in choosing a location (own illustration).

when choosing a location. Specific housing requirements and the living environment, which again consist of both hard and soft factors, also play a role. The participants attached great importance to the liveability of the residential area, the proximity to retail facilities, especially for daily needs and to the city centre, but also to green and recreational areas. Soft location factors play a role, particularly with regard to social aspects such as a good neighbourhood, a pleasant residential area that is perceived as safe and clean.

The relevance of the location factor of cultural offerings in the analysis may be due to the specific target group in the ‘Testing the City’-project, as the participants often needed cultural facilities for their professional activities, as most of the people working in the cultural and creative industries were looking for an exchange with local institutions. Nevertheless, the relevance of other leisure and gastronomy offerings and, in particular, the frequently emphasized importance of recreational opportunities and landscape attractiveness showed that factors for leisure activities and recreation are just as central. Flexible working time models and an irregular, mostly project-related constant change between intensive work phases and more quiet phases, which is typical for the target group, could be the reason for the high importance of short-term and quickly accessible leisure and recreation opportunities (Waitt & Gibson, 2009; Lorenzen, 2018).

Since the retail and service offerings of a medium-sized city are not comparable to those of a large city, and this was not expected by the participants in most cases, the connection to large cities and agglomerations plays a central role in being able to access certain offers and facilities. In addition, the accessibility of large cities can also be relevant for employment if appointments or project agreements have to be made in these cities. The survey analysis clearly shows that the connection of a medium-sized city to a large city by public transport and in particular a train connection between the cities is relevant. The use of local public transport beyond city and regional borders is based on an ecological motivation it is seen as an optimization of working time, as the journey time can be used for mobile working if appropriate conditions, such as an internet connection on the train, are available. Subsequently, the mobility options within the city, which should enable uncomplicated everyday life, are another relevant aspect in the location choice, which emerges from the survey results. A good connection to local public transport, but also a well-developed network of cycle paths and footpaths were important to the participants in order to cover distances within the city as independently and individually as possible. Here, too, a reference can be made to the situation in large cities, where traffic jams and traffic congestion are often cited as negative side effects due to the high level of population.

The participants considered the availability of open spaces, in form of physical spaces but also general opportunities to develop new concepts and ideas, and the openness of urban society as important for economic establishment in a location. In the Görlitz case study, many participants in the ‘Testing the City’-project used their stay to offer their services, but also to try out ideas or concepts. To do this, they were dependent on an open-minded local population in order to receive feedback on their offers and gain experiences. A stable internet connection also proved to be a highly relevant hard location factor for almost every activity. Finally, the participants rated typical characteristics of a medium-sized city, such as spatial and social proximity and a good overview of

the city, as an advantage of the city type. It is noticeable here that these factors primarily had an effect when trying out the location as part of the project. Often not considered as relevant by the participants before the project participation, the short distances within the city proved to be a significant advantage. The ability to reach various destinations in the city in a relatively short time meant that everyday life slowed down to a certain extent, as there were no long commutes.

Advantages and disadvantages of medium-sized cities

The perception that large cities, with their increasingly negative signs of congestion, are no longer perceived as suitable places to live, but that people are looking for a location that still offers a certain level of urban facilities (Federal Foundation of Baukultur, 2016), was confirmed by the participants in the analysis. Over 80% of participants stated that they would like to live in a medium-sized city in the future. Even if biases due to the project taking place in a medium-sized city are possible, the desire to live in an urban environment is evident. The following translated interview quote from a project participant illustrates this:

I believe that a medium-sized city is an ideal place for people from large cities. Because these people don't want to live without certain things and a medium-sized city can offer that, or a city of up to 100,000 people can offer that and still have the freedom to try things out.

When comparing the city types of large and medium-sized cities with each other, the participants of the project 'Testing the City' appreciated above all the calm and deceleration in medium-sized cities. This was favoured by less traffic in the city, faster access to various destinations due to short distances within the city, as well as quick access to the surrounding landscape. Additionally, the analysis confirms other studies in which soft location factors such as spatial and social proximity, networks and a high level of social cohesion as well as a committed civil society and a good sense of security in the city are often cited as potentials of medium-sized cities (Vaillant *et al.*, 2012; Kwiatek-Sołtys & Mainet, 2014; Mainet & Edouard, 2018). Furthermore, this study shows peripheral medium-sized cities affected by shrinkage offer abundant supply of spaces for living and also for the implementation of creative concepts or new project ideas.

The advantages highlighted by the Görlitz case study are characteristics that generally characterize medium-sized cities. A compact city with short distances, spatial opportunities for creative or artistic development and local recreational opportunities in the surrounding landscape, which are usually also due to the peripheral location far away from large cities, are factors that can also be found in a similar cities (Brabazon, 2015; Schmidt-Lauber, 2017). Another crucial factor, which was particularly important in the Görlitz case study, was the opportunity to get involved locally and support to design the own living environment. The existing commitment within urban society encouraged some participants to contribute through private or commercial activities to create currently missing offers themselves or to show new ways of realisation within the city.

Many of the participants lived in a large city with more than 100,000 people they were, therefore, able to make comparison between the two types of city after the trial stay in a medium-sized city. Work and employment opportunities continue to be a major

advantage of large cities and agglomerations, which cannot be fully compensated by the increasing shortage of skilled workers in rural areas and peripheral cities. The survey results only show that this advantage of a large city is not significant for people who primarily work digitally or can offer their products on an online market. With regard to the greater variety of offers in large cities in terms of culture, gastronomy, retail and leisure, there was a sense of uncertainty among the participants as to whether these offers are really relevant in a location. Many offers are also not perceived in large cities, but larger city types offer the (theoretical) opportunity to do so, which is often not the case in medium-sized cities.

Location choice process

Additional interviews with former project participants proved that the decision to relocate and thus to move to a new location is a complex and individual process that is often made up of a combination of different factors and framework conditions. The motives of the participants for looking for a new place to live were mostly based on dissatisfaction with the conditions at their current place of residence. This study shows that people are interested in relocating when they can no longer find adequate housing in their current location to react to changes in their private or professional life.

Even if you could afford the flat, you wouldn't be able to afford a creative workspace of 70 square metres and not just one staircase down. So there are constellations here that you can only really realise in an environment that is somehow more relaxed, not as dense as Berlin is dense or other metropolises are dense (translated quote of a project participant).

The survey results once again clearly show that developments in large cities and agglomerations in particular are motivating people to search for a new location.

The survey results highlight two main reasons for choosing a location in a peripheral medium-sized city affected by shrinkage, without considering these to be the only relevant factors in the specific relocation decision. Above all, a personal connection, such as family or friendship relations or a fascination for a place, was an incentive to choose this location. In addition to this emotional motivation, a more rational motivation can also influence the choice of location. The possibility of being able to pursue a professional activity in an environment that offers better conditions than a large city is a significant factor here and, in the case of a location in a medium-sized city affected by shrinkage, is based in particular on the availability of space.

While the decision for a location is often influenced by several factors, the decision against a location in the survey data is influenced in particular by the employment situation or the possibility of being able to pursue own profession at a location. If people are dependent on clients or sales markets in the regional or local area, a medium-sized city in a peripheral and often structurally weak location can have disadvantages. Similar to other studies, the criteria of job opportunities in a location are considered to be more relevant than the quality of life in a location (Arntz, 2010; Etzo, 2011; Buch *et al.*, 2014). On the other hand, for people who are not tied to a specific location due to their employment, the survey results confirm studies that show that the perceived quality of life in a location does play a role in the choice of location for this group of people (Niedomysl & Hansen, 2010; Rodríguez-Pose & Ketterer, 2012; Fertner *et al.*, 2015).

However, a temporary stay in a potentially new location contributes significantly to making the ‘right’ decision in the long term. Since the additional interviews were conducted in spring 2021, it was also possible to discuss a reflection on the choice of location made or possibly still to be made against the background of the coronavirus pandemic. The survey results show that households are increasingly and more intensively considering a potential new place to live, and that the pandemic has further intensified existing thoughts of moving.

Strengths and potentials of peripheral medium-sized cities affected by shrinkage

From the findings, the author derives strengths and potentials to be fostered for peripheral medium-sized cities affected by shrinkage. The ‘Testing the City’ project has provided detailed findings for Görlitz. Nevertheless, the city is also representative of many medium-sized cities, particularly in eastern Germany, which have had to accept similar developments over the last 30 years and are currently stabilising. In view of demographic developments and current migration movements, many medium-sized cities in Germany and across Europe will also face the challenge of dealing with shrinking processes in the future, while remaining attractive locations and ensuring their preservation and revitalisation by attracting new people (Wolff & Wiechmann, 2017).

A self-confident and targeted marketing of the available housing, an emphasis on the local specificity of the cities and thereby the concentration on interested target groups as well as a future urban development that also allows room for experimental approaches can contribute to making this city type becoming an alternative location to large cities.

The survey results underscore the importance of suitable and accessible housing in relocation decisions. However, an existing, large supply of housing does not automatically become a locational advantage if needs cannot be met or access to this supply is not transparent. Due to varying life stages, work conditions and lifestyles, people increasingly seek flexible housing options – such as larger apartments with spaces that separate work and private life. An increasing relevance of flexible forms of housing, the desire for participatory design of the living space as well as for shared forms of housing has also been observed in other scientific surveys for some years now (Förster *et al.*, 2020). However, Görlitz currently lacks a clearly structured and accessible housing presentation, in part due to limited municipal resources. Challenges such as unclear property ownership, heritage protection rules and neglected historic buildings further complicate inner-city revitalization efforts. Many historic buildings that have not been maintained for many years are at risk of being completely destroyed in the coming years. The city of Görlitz has launched an initiative to identify potential uses for these buildings in line with existing heritage protection requirements. The Urban Transformation Matrix is an innovative tool that could support future planning. However, a lack of personnel capacity in particular, as well as inconsistencies in the application of the tool, are currently preventing further utilisation (Knippschild & Zöllter, 2021).

The age groups of 31 to 40-year-olds and 51 to 60-year-olds were the most strongly represented among the project applications. Understanding which target groups find medium-sized cities attractive is crucial for effective communication and marketing. Not everyone values these cities equally, but the data shows that people in specific life phases

or with certain lifestyles are more likely to seek alternatives to large cities – be it for family reasons, limited space in their current city, or health concerns like pollution. Targeted advertising of various advantages of smaller cities, such as ‘family-friendly living’ or living in a scenically attractive environment, can provide support here in order to be perceived as a potential residential location alternative to large cities. Many cities are already starting to advertise their potential on the housing market and their quality of life. The project experience made it clear that more effort than just marketing is required to really tie interested people to a location, especially if they have many other locations to choose from. Personalised support that provides links to the housing market, potential networks for work and family infrastructures increases the likelihood that people will identify with the city, want to stay and help to shape it (Projektverbund Stadt der Zukunft auf Probe, 2024). Likewise, the perspective of the existing urban population should not be overlooked and an urban development concept should work integrative for all user groups in order to prevent undesirable developments (VanHoose *et al.*, 2021). Our study shows that many of the critical points raised by project participants are also points of criticism from the local population.

The experimental approach in the ‘Testing the City’-project on which this work is based has shown that trying out a location for a limited period of time is a way for people to become aware of a potential location choice. In general, such an offer is aimed at people who are considering a move but still have certain concerns or see obstacles that can perhaps be overcome by a trial stay. In addition, the innovative character of the project also draws people’s attention to a previously unknown or unavailable location. With such an offer, a city shows an innovative character and the ambition to do something for its own development and sustainability. This approach can also appeal to people from outside and get them excited about a location. Other models for trying out or temporarily living in a new location have also developed in recent years. Examples include the ‘Summer of Pioneers’ and the ‘*KoDorf*’ and ‘*Hof Prädikow*’ initiatives. In cooperation with municipalities, companies and civil society, they all aim to contribute to new solutions for a diverse community life and the development of the places with a focus on the common welfare (Netzwerk Zukunftsorte, 2022). Even if these projects rarely work with such intensive scientific accompaniment as the ‘Testing the City’-project presented here, similar experiences are made in the municipalities with regard to relocation motivations, location factors and location decisions.

Conclusion

The survey results show that hard location factors are included in a location decision when it comes to the general framework conditions for living and daily activities within a city. In addition, the ‘well-being’ at a location is also important, which is often reflected in soft location factors. While hard factors make everyday life possible, soft factors are above all those aspects that make everyday life easier or more pleasant and enable a ‘work-life balance’ with recreational and leisure activities.

This paper analysed possible strengths and potentials of medium-sized cities as attractive residential and living locations against the background of a stabilization of polycentric structures in Germany. By attempting to balance the pressures faced by densely populated large cities and urban agglomerations with the challenges of shrinking

and peripheral medium-sized cities, regional imbalances in housing markets can be mitigated. In addition to the potential offered by the existing supply of housing for medium-sized cities, it is essential to adopt a comprehensive, nation-wide perspective on housing policy in Germany. As outlined earlier, the German government has announced a housing construction offensive of 400,000 new homes per year due to the tight housing markets in many large German cities and agglomerations. However, this ambition stands in complete contrast to principles of resource-efficient and sustainable urban development. Demolishing underused housing in one area while simultaneously constructing new homes elsewhere – often on previously unbuilt land – leads to increased land sealing, substantial resource consumption and negative impacts on the climate balance (Umweltbundesamt, 2021; Knippschild *et al.*, 2025). A more future-oriented and ecologically mindful approach would focus on the revitalization of existing housing stock and the strengthening of multifunctional city centres as attractive places to live. This strategy could significantly reduce further increasing dispersion and thus land consumption in suburbs and agglomerations. Furthermore, targeted investment in high-quality urban life in smaller, often peripheral cities supports the constitutional aim of equivalent living conditions across different regions (BMWSB, 2023). In the case of Görlitz – but also in other cities with mostly historic city centres – this revitalization also contributes to the preservation of cultural heritage.

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